

Minute-long quantum coherence enabled by electrical depletion of magnetic noise

Cyrus Zeledon¹, Benjamin Pingault^{2,1}, Jonathan C. Marcks^{2,1}, Mykyta Onizhuk¹, Yeghishe Tsaturyan¹, Yu-xin Wang³, Benjamin S. Soloway¹, Hiroshi Abe⁴, Misagh Ghezellou⁵, Jawad Ul-Hassan⁵, Takeshi Ohshima^{4,6}, Nguyen T. Son⁵, F. Joseph Heremans^{2,1}, Giulia Galli¹, Christopher P. Anderson⁷, David D. Awschalom^{1,2,*}

¹*Pritzker School of Molecular Engineering, University of Chicago, Chicago, Illinois 60637, USA*

²*Center for Molecular Engineering and Materials Science Division, Argonne National Laboratory, Lemont, IL 60439, USA*

³*Joint Center for Quantum Information and Computer Science, University of Maryland, College Park, MD 20742, USA*

⁴*National Institutes for Quantum and Radiological Science and Technology, 1233 Watanuki, Takasaki, Gunma 370-1292, Japan*

⁵*Department of Physics, Chemistry and Biology, Linköping University, SE-581 83 Linköping, Sweden*

⁶*Department of Materials Science, Tohoku University, Aoba, Sendai, Miyagi 980-8579, Japan*

⁷*Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL 61801, USA*

* Corresponding author. Email: awsch@uchicago.edu

Abstract

Integrating solid-state spin defects into classical electronic devices can enable new opportunities for quantum information processing that benefit from existing semiconductor technology. We show, through bias control of an isotopically purified silicon carbide (SiC) p-i-n diode, the depletion of not only electrical noise sources but also magnetic noise sources, resulting in record coherences for SiC electron spin qubits. We also uncover complementary improvements to the relaxation times of nuclear spin registers controllable by the defect, and measure diode-enhanced coherences. These improvements lead to record-long nuclear spin Hahn-echo times on the scale of minutes. These results demonstrate the power of materials control and electronic device integration to create highly coherent solid-state quantum network nodes and processors.

Introduction

Electron spin defects in the solid state are promising platforms for quantum communication (1) and quantum sensing (2, 3-5) because of their spin-photon interface (6, 7), long coherence times (8-10), high-fidelity single-shot readout (8, 11), and coupling to nuclear spins as local memories (9, 10). These systems have formed the backbone of nascent quantum networks around the world (14, 15) and unlocked precise sensing at the nanoscale (16, 17). Despite advancements in defect qubit performance, uncontrolled charge and spin bath dynamics within the material limit the spin and optical coherence for these systems (18, 19), which stymies many of these applications. Specifically, paramagnetic impurities and naturally occurring nuclear spin isotopes can cause magnetic fluctuations that decohere both the central electron spin and surrounding nuclear spin qubits. To remedy limitations of coherence from magnetic noise, a multitude of approaches have been explored, including nuclear spin reduction via isotopic engineering (12, 20, 21), Hamiltonian engineering to reduce the impact of the noisy bath dynamics on qubits (8, 22-24), and growth to reduce paramagnetic impurities (19, 26, 27). On the other hand, the electronic and charge noise effects on defects have been tackled through semiconductor device engineering (25-27), growth to reduce unwanted traps that cause electric field instabilities (25-27), and annealing of the material to eliminate crystal vacancies (21, 28, 29). However, none of these demonstrations have shown in-situ tunability or mitigation of both the electronic and magnetic environment simultaneously, needed to improve the electron and nuclear spin coherence beyond the current state of the art. In addition, the control of magnetic noise sources beyond purifying the nuclear spin environment remains limited.

Silicon carbide (SiC), a promising quantum platform, is a wafer-scale semiconductor widely used in the high-power electronics industry owing to its high temperature performance and doping capabilities. Its large bandgap and naturally low nuclear spin content also make it an excellent host for optically active spin defects (30). Among these defects, the neutral divacancy (VV^0) (31), consisting of neighboring silicon and carbon vacancies, has attracted attention due to its optically interfaced electron spin ($S = 1$), making it a promising building block for quantum networks (12, 26, 32, 33) and quantum sensing (34, 35). However, electric noise is known to cause spectral diffusion and large inhomogeneous optical and spin linewidths for quantum emitters such as the VV^0 (23, 36-39). Previous advances with SiC defects embedded in diode structures have demonstrated a dramatic 50-fold reduction of the optical linewidth (26), as well as tunability and stabilization of the emission wavelength. This occurs from a biasing of the diode into depletion, reducing the presence of unwanted electric field fluctuations and charge traps (26). In parallel, isotopic purification of SiC has been employed to reduce the nuclear spin content, resulting in improved electron spin coherence (12, 40).

Our approach combines, for the first time, a doped diode structure with isotopic engineering to achieve state-of-the-art performance of individual electron spins and their nuclear spin registers. Unexpectedly, we observe that the diode control not only improves optical linewidths by reducing spectral diffusion, but also improves the electron and nuclear spin coherence. By voltage tuning the device, we achieve near lifetime-limited optical linewidths and a factor of two improvement in electron spin Ramsey coherence, greater than 300 μ s, between forward and reverse bias. In this highly coherent platform, we then leverage the dilute nuclear spin environment to demonstrate initialization, control, and readout of a single, weakly coupled ^{29}Si nuclear spin. We measure Ramsey and Hahn echo coherence times approaching a second and multiple minutes, respectively, exceeding previous state-of-the-art solid state nuclear spin

coherence times in any material by over an order-of-magnitude (41-45). This not only furthers our understanding of the impact of parasitic noise sources on solid-state qubits, but also demonstrates how simultaneous active electric and magnetic engineering in a device can dramatically improve solid-state qubit performance and functionality.

Results

Isolated single defects in an isotopically purified semiconductor device

We first identify and control a single, axial VV^0 (PL2) (32) in a custom-grown isotopically purified 4H-SiC p-i-n diode (Fig. 1a). Optical Stark shifts represent the effect of the local electric field on the VV^0 defect's optical excited state in forward and reverse bias (Fig. 1b). We also observe minimal optical line shifts between 0 V to 40 V of reverse bias, corresponding to the formation of a depletion region that traverses to the depth of the defect (26). The device displays rectifying behavior at 5 K in a current-voltage (I-V) sweep, where we observe low leakage currents (10s of nA) for large applied reverse bias (~ 100 V), allowing for large tunability (Fig. 1b). From multiple sweeps of photoluminescence excitation (PLE), we observe the E_x optical line is stable over the course of 1 hour with an inhomogeneous broadening of 20.8 (2) MHz (Supplementary Materials) while under 80 V of reverse bias. The narrowest averaged PLE scan over the course of the stability measurement gives a linewidth of 14(2) MHz close to the Fourier lifetime limit of ~ 11 MHz, consistent with our observed optical lifetime decay of 15(1) ns.

Diode-dependent behavior of the defect

To understand the effect of electric field tuning on our defect's optical and spin properties, we first characterize the voltage-dependent optical linewidth and compare it to the spin coherence. We observe a three-fold improvement to the E_x optical linewidth from ~ 80 MHz at 0 V to ~ 20 MHz after reaching full depletion at -60 V (Fig. 1c, top). This confirms the reduction in electrical noise near the defect from fluctuating charge traps, as the optical linewidth of the VV^0 center does not depend on magnetic noise due to the very similar g-factor in the ground and excited states (26).

We then explore the effects of depletion on the defect's electron spin, which is nominally sensitive mostly to magnetic noise and only weakly to electric noise (36, 37). Previous results in isotopically engineered 4H-SiC material demonstrated Hahn-echo coherence times of 2.3 ms for VV^0 and 0.8 ms for V_{Si} , which are lower than nuclear spin-limited theoretical values (\sim tens of ms for both defects (12, 40)), given the level of isotopic purification. Previous works attributed this reduction to cracks in the material from processing (40) and unaccounted-for paramagnetic spins that cause the central electron spins in the material to decohere faster than expected (12). While we expect depletion to improve the uncontrolled fluctuating electric fields (26), we hypothesize that it can also deplete unwanted paramagnetic sources of a particular spin-containing charge state, such as V_{Si} , N, and V_C , to a charge state with inherent 0-spin (46), improving coherence.

To test the hypothesis that depletion of paramagnetic sources will improve coherence, we measure Ramsey and Hahn echo coherence at different applied biases in the diode. With 120 V in forward bias, we observe broadened optical linewidths, compared to 0 V, of 99(1) MHz and a T_2^* of 153(16) μ s. As reverse bias is applied, we observe that the Ramsey dephasing rate decreases with a qualitatively similar trend to the decrease in the optical linewidth (Fig. 1c,

middle). The longest Ramsey dephasing time we measure is 320(30) μs , over a 52% improvement from 0 V applied bias (Supplementary Materials). This value is the longest reported for defects in SiC, enabled by the depletion in the semiconductor device, and is significantly longer than the ab initio cluster correlated expansion (CCE) predicted value of 54 μs at this isotope concentration (12). We then perform double-quantum (DQ) Ramsey measurements (Fig. 2a) and find that the DQ T_2^* at both 0 V and 80 V of reverse bias are almost exactly half (within the error) that of single quantum Ramsey decay times (Supplementary Materials), confirming that the coherence remains magnetically-limited at both bias voltages (36). Therefore, the limit for both cases is magnetic, so an improvement in the coherence is confirmed to be a reduction in the magnetic noise. We also observe that Hahn echo decay times display a qualitatively similar voltage-dependent trend as the optical linewidth and Ramsey values (Fig. 1c, bottom). Our measured Hahn echo decay times show a 24% improvement in depletion (Supplementary Materials). The comparable improvements in the Hahn echo and Ramsey values suggest that we have eliminated sources of both slow ($\sim\text{Hz}$) and fast ($\sim\text{kHz}$) magnetic noise, likely from paramagnetic impurities. Despite this, the Hahn-echo times still remain lower than the calculated nuclear-spin limited value.

From the Hahn echo decays of the electron spin, we find an exponential-decay stretch factor of $n \approx 1.5$ while in the undepleted state, corresponding to dynamic interaction from our VV^0 with a paramagnetic spin bath (47, 48). In depletion, the stretch factor converges to $n \approx 2$, suggesting that the defect is limited by $1/f$ -type noise (49), which can be explained by coupling to an interacting dipolar spin bath (50) (see Supplementary Materials).

Understanding slow noise

We then perform a Ramsey measurement for 22.5 hours to understand the dynamics of the slow noise for both 0 and 80 V of reverse bias (Fig. 2b). In both of these experiments, we observe characteristic drops and resurgences of the Ramsey signal that occur from a single weakly-coupled nuclear spin, as seen and described in Ref. (41). These weakly-coupled nuclear spins are not common because their observation requires a balance between isotopic concentration and proximity to the defect (1-2 nm away). We also observed that at 0 V, there are also variations in the Ramsey oscillation frequency, indicative of shifts in local magnetic field. On the other hand, in depletion (-80 V), the frequency is much more stable and the inversions of the Ramsey signal are clearer. By measuring the Ramsey signal at a delay corresponding to the hyperfine coupling (41) and monitoring it over the course of the 22.5 hours, we measure the nuclear spin state in a quantum non-demolition (QND) manner. Surprisingly, we observe that the diode also impacts the T_1 relaxation time of the nucleus by a factor of 2 (Fig. 2c). A histogram of QND measurement of the nuclear register while under depletion is shown in Fig. 2d. From this repetitive readout, we achieve single-shot detection of the nuclear spin state with a fidelity of 98.6%.

Coherent control and coherence of isolated ^{29}Si Nuclei

To understand the improvements of the nuclear T_1 relaxation time, and utilize this register, we control the weakly coupled nucleus using a highly selective method of dynamical decoupling and explore its coherence properties. Previous results demonstrated nanoscale NMR of weakly coupled nuclei in isotopically purified SiC (12), but there are no measurements to-date of the control and coherence properties of these potential quantum registers. Here, we explore the coherent control and coherence of a single ^{29}Si nucleus, corroborating the effect of electric field

tuning of spin coherence. We use an XY8-based dynamical decoupling to implement initialization and control gates on the ^{29}Si nuclear spin mediated by the VV^0 electron. The nuclear spin resonance spectroscopy shows periodic resonances in the coherence function when the interpulse time is set to $\tau_k \approx \frac{(2k+1)\pi}{2\omega_l + A_{\parallel}}$, where k is the integer order of the resonance dips and ω_l is the Larmor frequency of ^{29}Si (Fig. 3a). The observed resonances are consistent with a single weakly coupled ^{29}Si nuclear spin.

After identifying the target nuclear register, we initialize and readout the spin (Fig. 3b) and proceed to coherently drive Rabi oscillations of the isolated nucleus (Fig. 3c) (53, 54). We identify and determine the hyperfine parameters — $a_{\parallel} = -8.1(1)$ kHz and $a_{\perp} = 9.4(1)$ kHz — from the resonance dip that match the electron Ramsey frequencies and the change in magnetic state of the VV^0 , which affects the Ramsey nuclear precession frequency. Utilizing these nuclear spin control sequences, we measure the coherence properties of the ^{29}Si nuclear spin in the diode. Spin-to-charge conversion (SCC) is implemented for these long nuclear spin coherence measurements to boost the signal-to-noise ratio (8). We find that without any bias, the Ramsey interferometry of this nuclear spin yields 377(26) ms when the VV^0 is prepared in $m_s = 0$ (Fig. 4a). Surprisingly, the nuclear spin T_2^* at 80 V of reverse bias is extended to 521(12) ms when the electron spin is prepared in $m_s = 0$ (Fig. 4a). We therefore find that the electric field tuning affects not only the electron spin but the nuclear spin as well, with a $\sim 40\%$ improvement in dephasing time, similar to the improvement seen in the electron spin T_2^* of $\sim 52\%$. We would expect these improvements to be similar given that the same paramagnetic species that limit the VV^0 would also affect the nuclear spins in the material. In addition, we find that the coherence times are affected by the frozen core effect when the electron spin state is prepared in $m_s = -1$. This occurs because the VV^0 electron spin induces a hyperfine field with a strong gradient on nearby nuclear spins that suppresses the transfer of polarization between nuclei, benefiting the coherence time of the target spin (55). In this situation, we measure a nuclear spin T_2^* of 690(44) ms while in reverse bias (Fig. 4a).

It is interesting to note that the enhancement factors in the nuclear spin Ramsey time versus its T_1 relaxation time follows a simple scaling relation of $T_2^*(-80\text{V}) / T_2^*(0\text{V}) \simeq \sqrt{T_1(-80\text{V}) / T_1(0\text{V})}$. Such a scaling law agrees with the microscopic spin-bath model where both nuclear Ramsey dephasing and relaxation are due to the same ensemble of weakly interacting magnetic impurities, see Supplementary Materials (13, 48).

Finally, we measure the Hahn echo time of the single ^{29}Si spin, demonstrating a coherence time of 10.2(6) s when the electron spin is prepared in $m_s = 0$ state (Fig. 4b). We find the stretch factor of the Gaussian Hahn-echo decay to also be $n = 2$, confirming the $1/f$ noise seen by the VV^0 . When the electron is instead prepared in $m_s = -1$, the frozen core effect dramatically increases this coherence time, showing negligible decay over our longest delay time of 30 seconds. Using a chi-squared goodness of fit test with 99% confidence, and assuming a stretch exponent $n = 1$ ($n = 2$), we find a lower bound of over 630 s (120 s) (Fig. 4b). We confirm these observations using second-order CCE simulations that predict that due to the frozen core, Hahn echo decay times can be up to minutes long in our magnetic and charge noise-free environment (see Supplementary Materials). Our measurements therefore demonstrate the power of electric fields to tune the coherences beyond just the optical domain and enable long-lived memory qubits that outperform any nuclear spin coupled to a quantum emitter without a clock transition (41-45).

We attribute these improvements across all optical and spin measurements in SiC to the simultaneous depletion of paramagnetic traps and electrical noise near the defect and other affected spin species. The improvements to the electron and nuclear T_2^* may suggest that the main source of decoherence now stems strictly from nuclear spins in the material. Of the likely paramagnetic defects, we expect that the amount of V_{Si} from irradiation and growth will be negligible after our annealing steps (51), leaving both N and V_C as potential sources of magnetic noise with the appropriate parasitic spin state. Generally, materials grown via chemical vapor-deposition have defect densities below 10^{14} cm^{-3} , causing a fundamental limit in the coherences of defect spins. The most likely traps that are fully depleted as a source of magnetic noise are carbon vacancies and nitrogen dopants, which have $S = 3/2$ and $S = 1/2$ in the -1 and 0 charge state respectively (which occurs with a mid-gap Fermi level) (52). Therefore, we ascribe the mechanism of the observed coherence improvement to the reduction in magnetic noise from nitrogen impurities and carbon vacancies, which are both depleted into positively charged $S = 0$ states under the 705 nm illumination used in our experiment (52). Unfortunately, even with this improvement, the measured Hahn echo value still remains an order of magnitude lower than predictions from ab initio CCE calculations (Supplemental Materials), requiring further investigation. These results demonstrate that a quantum emitter in a material platform with simultaneous parasitic electric and magnetic noise can be mitigated in-situ to improve its optical and spin properties with a simple semiconductor diode.

Conclusions and outlook

Here, we discover that electrical depletion allows us to extend the lifetime and coherences of both electron and nuclear spins to record values (56) by eliminating both electric field fluctuations and paramagnetic noise sources. We find an improvement to the electron spin coherence by more than 50% of non-depleted values, and a surprising order-of-magnitude longer nuclear spin Hahn echo decay when compared to any other platform. These extended coherence times are ideal for quantum information protocols that require long-lived, local registers that can serve as memory qubits. Overall, the diode-embedded defect platform presented here demonstrates the promise of integrating classical and quantum optoelectronics into wafer-scale quantum technology. The presented depletion technique can be readily applied to other qubits in semiconductors that are limited by electric field fluctuations (21, 57, 58) or paramagnetic sources (39, 57, 58).

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Author contributions:

Conceptualization: C.Z., D.D.A. Experimental measurement: C.Z., B.P. Device fabrication: C.Z., Y.T. Data analysis: C.Z., B.P., J.C.M., C.P.A. Experimental setup development: C.Z., C.P.A., B.P., J.C.M., B.S.S. Theoretical understanding: Y.-X.W., M.O. Theoretical calculations: M.O. Electron irradiation: H.A., T.O. SiC p-i-n design and epitaxial growth: J.U.-H., M.G. Theoretical supervision: G.G. Supervision: D.D.A. Writing (review and editing): All authors contributed to manuscript preparation.

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Fig. 1. p-i-n diode and tuning the embedded VV^0 environment. (a) Schematic of the diode structure showing spins studied. (b) Current-voltage (I-V) curve (purple) of the diode and Stark Shift (red) of the VV^0 $m_s = 0$ optical transition. The three different colored panels show depletion (blue), minimal optical shifts (light gray), and forward bias Stark shifts (pink). (c) Optical linewidth of the divacancy's E_x transition (top), Ramsey dephasing rate (middle), and Hahn echo dephasing rate (bottom) as a function of applied bias. The shaded region is a guide for the eye to show the onset of depletion at the defect. All data are taken at ~ 232 Gauss and at $T = 5$ K.

Fig. 2. Understanding the noise and spin-related effects. (a) Double quantum Ramsey interference of a single divacancy at 0 V and 80 V of reverse bias. (b) (top) A 22.5 hour scan of the $m_s = 0$ to $m_s = -1$ transition of the VV^0 while under 0 V of reverse bias showing slow variations of the VV^0 spin frequency throughout the scan. (bottom) A 22.5 hour scan of the $m_s = 0$ to $m_s = -1$ transition of the VV^0 while under 80 V of reverse bias showing stable VV^0 spin frequency. A detuning of ~ 10 kHz is used for both scans. Integration time per point is 1 s and each Ramsey scan took 57.5 s on average. The dashed lines in both plots bound the regions for the rolling average line cut in (c) (c) (middle and bottom) Shifted differential of the 0 and -1 fluorescence time trace showing single-shot readout of the nuclear spin and corresponding quantum jumps. The red is the nuclear down state and the blue is the nuclear up state. The dashed lines are the thresholds that maximize readout fidelity. (d) Histogram of the counts from the repetitive readout demonstrating the overlap of the two distributions of the nuclear spin states.

Fig. 3. Coherent control of a single ^{29}Si nuclear spin. (a) Pulse sequence for nuclear spin spectroscopy using XY8-N dynamical decoupling sequence on VV^0 (top). The rotation ($R_{x/y}^\theta$) gates represent rotation of the electron spin by an angle θ around the given axis of the Bloch sphere, and “Init” and “Read” refer to the optical pulses to initialize and readout the electron spin state. The measurement is of the final VV^0 spin population in $|0\rangle$ using an XY8-4 sequence as a function of the interpulse time τ (bottom). The blue circles represent the experimental data and the light blue line represent a simulation based on the hyperfine coupling parameters $\{a_{\parallel} = -8.1$ kHz and $a_{\perp} = 9.4$ kHz $\}$. (b) Pulse sequence for the nuclear spin initialization and readout gates (top). The conditional rotations are executed with XY8 sequences on the VV^0 spin. The measured (circles) and simulated (solid line) values of the VV^0 spin projection after the nuclear initialization and readout gates are presented as a function of interpulse delay τ for the different spin states of VV^0 . The optimal measured delay time for highest initialization fidelity is $\tau = 3.715$ μs . (c) Pulse sequence (top) and measurement (bottom) for coherent control of the isolated, single nuclear spin and the measured Rabi oscillations. Light blue line represents a sine fit over the data. All data with $\langle\sigma_z\rangle$ is the spin projection with the SCC readout normalized to its contrast.

Fig. 4. Coherences of a single ^{29}Si nuclear spin. (a) Pulse sequence and diode dependent measurement for Ramsey interference of the nuclear spin when the electron is prepared in $m_s = 0$ (light blue and light red) and $m_s = -1$ (light purple), where pulses are the same as in Fig. 3(c). The Ramsey data at each point is fitted and the amplitudes and associated errors then plotted. **(b)** Hahn echo pulse sequence and measurement of the nuclear spin when the electron is prepared in $m_s = 0$ (light blue) and $m_s = -1$ (light purple). The dashed purple denotes an optical initialization and then pi pulse to the $m_s = -1$ spin state. All data with $\langle \sigma_z \rangle$ is the spin projection with the SCC readout normalized to its contrast.